

DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE SPEAKING OF STUDENTS THROUGH SMART TECHNOLOGIES

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Communicative foreign language instruction is one of the key components of the modernization of Uzbek education concept. The construction and development of future specialists with communicative language competency is the goal of the required "Foreign language" discipline in the state-mandated vocational education system. The development of students' communicative language abilities will enable them to participate in professional foreign language communication, recognize their personal and professional demands, and take advantage of business relationships that offer opportunities for professional growth and self-education. The advancement of information technology has created new opportunities for foreign language instruction. Their use lowers the psychological barrier associated with utilizing a foreign language for communication, boosts students' motivation and cognitive activity, and piques their interest in the subject.

Wiki technology is one of the tools for teaching foreign languages language. Since it is a content collaboration technology, it allows multiple users to edit the same material together. Wiki technologies can be used to develop skills in working with different types of texts (documents, articles, etc.), analyzing specific linguistic phenomena in the text, developing consistent skills in written translation, and presenting information in the text in an extended or condensed form. They can also be used to summarize the content of multiple texts or individual text fragments. When teaching a foreign language using wiki technology, a teacher's job is to choose text and audio resources while considering the group's and each student's individual language proficiency, training level, volume, and the lexical and grammatical content to be covered. Every student's work must be coordinated by the teacher, who can also point out errors by highlighting them in different colors (red for grammatical errors, yellow for order words, blue for spelling errors, pink for lexical errors, etc.), make notes on each page, and plan a discussion of the lesson's outcomes.

It is impossible to communicate without the ability to understand spoken foreign languages by hearing.

One of the most crucial and challenging aspects of teaching a foreign language, especially a second language, is developing the ability to perceive real speech by ear (listening).

We think using audio and videocasts is the most efficient. They provide you the chance to actively build and hone your listening comprehension abilities by having you listen to monologues and dialogic discourse in other languages at first slowly and then at a normal rate, followed by playback.

The word "podcast" (derived from the English words "iPod" and "broadcast") describes a free online audio or video clip that is shared for public consumption.

You have the option to listen to the files online or download them to your computer or another mobile device. In 2004, podcasts made their debut. [9] Benefits of podcasts include:

- allowing listeners to experience native speakers' speech in natural communication settings;
- updating content and vocabulary on a regular basis;
- making podcasts accessible to students through mobile devices like laptops and smartphones;

Emerging technologies do not take the place of traditional methods for teaching foreign languages in the classroom or serve as a panacea for all educational issues.

Innovative technology by themselves are unable to offer a thorough foundation for language learning. The proper integration of emerging technology into current, effectively implemented educational practices is essential if we are to maximize their potential.

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